
Research

Rwanda's post genocide peace building: developing society peace building

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Abstract: Efforts to restore the social structure that was shattered during the horrific events of 1994 is characterized by post-genocide Rwanda. The government created the National Unity and Reconciliation Commission (NURC) in 1999 to prepare reconciliation efforts. Rwanda has accomplished some remarkable milestones in the peace process at the state level. Reconciliation at the group and citizen levels, however, also poses major obstacles. It is imperative to develop the capacity for community dialogue to overcome the challenges. To ensure that an ecosystem able to accommodate and promote healing is successfully built at the grassroots level, the forums need even further investment instead of seeking to build new mechanisms and so, they need to use current reconciliation forums and improve upon them.

Keywords: Rwanda, United Nations, Peace Building, Genocide

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Accepted: 5 November, 2022; **Published:** 31 December, 2022

How to cite this article: Angel Yiadom Boachie (2022). *Rwanda's post genocide peace building: developing society peace building*. *North American Academic Research*, 5(11), 237-243. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7502190>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Efforts to restore the social structure that was shattered during the horrific events of 1994 is characterized by post-genocide Rwanda. The government created the National Unity and Reconciliation Commission (NURC) in 1999 to prepare reconciliation efforts. The NURC is a permanent, constitutionally protected body with a mandate to foster national unity and reconciliation in Rwanda after the genocide.

In the time of 1994 Rwandan genocide, members of the Hutu ethnic majority murdered as many as 800,000 people within the East-Central African country of Rwanda, mostly the Tutsi minority. The genocide spread throughout the country with shocking speed and brutality, launched by Hutu nationalists within the capital of Kigali, as ordinary citizens were encouraged by local officials as well as the Hutu Power government to be violent towards their neighbours. By the time a military offensive took control of the country by the Tutsi-led Rwandan Patriotic Front at the start of July, many thousands of Rwandans had died and two million refugees (mainly Hutus) had fled Rwanda, deepening what was already becoming a full-blown humanitarian crisis. In the early nineties, one of the highest population densities in Africa was recorded in Rwanda, a small country with a predominantly agricultural economy. Approximately 85 per cent of its population was Hutu; the remainder were Tutsi, including a small number of Twa, the original inhabitants of Rwanda, a Pygmy group. From 1897 to 1918, Rwanda became part of German East Africa, along with neighbouring

Burundi, a Belgian trusteeship under a League of Nations mandate after World War I. The colonial period of Rwanda, during which the ruling Belgians favoured the Tutsi minority over the Hutus, aggravated the tendency of the few to oppress the many, resulting in a legacy of hostility that erupted into bloodshed even before Rwanda's independence. There had always been disagreements between the majority Hutus and the minority Tutsis, but the two ethnic groups are quite similar because they speak the same language, live in the same regions and follow the same customs. However, after the colonial era, the rivalry between them grew significantly and when the Belgian colonists arrived in 1916, they developed identification cards classifying individuals according to their ethnicity. The Belgians considered that only the Tutsis were superior to the Hutus, causing the Tutsis to have more economic and educational prospects than their neighbours. In 1959, discontent among the Hutus eventually grew and resulted in a series of riots, killing more than 20,000 Tutsis and fleeing to neighbouring countries such as Burundi, Tanzania and Uganda. The Hutus took their place when Belgium granted Rwanda independence in 1962, and the Tutsis were the scapegoats for any crisis before the genocide. In 1959, a Hutu revolution forced as many as 330,000 Tutsis to flee the nation, which made them an even smaller minority. The triumphant Hutus had driven Rwanda's Tutsi monarchy into exile and declared the nation a republic by early 1961. Belgium gave Rwanda independence in July 1962, following a United Nations referendum in the same year. Ethnically driven violence persisted in the years following independence. A military faction placed Major General Juvenal Habyarimana, a progressive Hutu, in power in 1973. Habyarimana remained Rwanda's central authority for the next two decades, and he established a new political party, the National Revolutionary Movement for Development (NRMD). Under a new constitution ratified in 1978, he was elected president and re-elected in 1983 and 1988, when he was the primary candidate.

The Rwandan Patriotic Front (RPF) forces, comprised mostly of Tutsi refugees, invaded Rwanda from Uganda in 1990. Tutsi residents were accused by Habyarimana of being RPF collaborators and hundreds of them were arrested. The Tutsi massacres were instructed by state officials between 1990 and 1993, killing hundreds. On 20th April, in a report to the UNSC, the UNSG spoke of 'a torrent of widespread killings' and observed that 'the violence appears to have both political and ethnic dimensions' whose victims 'could number tens of thousands' (UN 1994b). [Eltringham, Nigel. 2004. *Accounting for horror: Post Genocide Debates in Rwanda*. London: Pluto Press.] The report, however, stated that the killings had been started by 'unruly members of the Presidential Guard' and implied that the real issue was fighting between the RPF and FAR, that a cease-fire between these two sides would end the violence. A UNSC resolution on 21 April, stated that it was 'appalled at the ensuing large-scale violence in Rwanda, which has resulted in the death of thousands of innocent civilians, but continued to associate the 'resolution of the Rwandan crisis' (the 'mindless violence and carnage which are engulfing Rwanda') with a cease-fire between the RPF and FAR (UN 1994c). [Ibid.] In a letter to the UNSC on 29 April, the UNSG stated that 'as many as 200,000 people may have died during the last three weeks' and recognised that the fighting between the RPF and FAR was distinct from 'massacres of innocent civilians on a massive scale caused by 'deep-rooted ethnic hatreds', although he still maintained that the massacres were due to 'uncontrolled military personnel' and the 'breakdown of law and order' (UN 1994d). [Ibid.]

In 1992, a ceasefire in these conflicts led to talks between the government and the RPF. In August 1993, in Arusha, Tanzania, Habyarimana signed an agreement calling for the creation of a transitional government that would include the RPF. Hutu extremists, who would soon take swift and horrible action to prevent it, were angered by this power-sharing agreement. A plane carrying Habyarimana and President Cyprien Ntaryamira of Burundi was shot down over Kigali, the capital, on April 6th, 1994, leaving no survivors. (It was never fully determined who the perpetrators were. Some accused extremists of the Hutu, while others accused RPF leaders.) Within an hour of the plane crash, the Presidential Guard set up roadblocks and barricades together with members of the Rwandan Armed Forces (FAR) and Hutu militia groups known as the Interahamwe ('Those Who Attack Together) and Impuzamugambi ('Those Who Have the Same Goal') and began with impunity to slaughter Tutsis and moderate Hutus. Moderate Hutu Prime Minister Agathe Uwilingiyimana and ten Belgian peacekeepers, killed on April 7th, were among the first victims of the genocide.

This violence created a political vacuum in which, on April 9th, the transitional government of extremist Hutu Power military high command leaders decided to step in. Meanwhile, the killing of Belgian peacekeepers had also provoked the withdrawal of Belgian troops, and from the U.N. Instructed that peacekeepers thereafter only defend themselves. There were twenty-five hundred United Nations peacekeepers on the ground, and indeed, soon after the killing began, the UN's force commander, Canadian General Romeo Dallaire, pleaded for a well-equipped battalion to stop the slaughter. Nonetheless, the UN instructed its soldiers not to protect the people right away. And on April 21, it ordered that all but 270 troops be withdrawn.[Barnett, Michael N. 2002. *Eyewitness to a Genocide: The United Nations and Rwanda*. 1st arg. Cornell University Press.] The fact of willful indifference continues to amaze. The Rwandan geno code is not only about the evil that is possible. It is also about the complacency exhibited by those who have the responsibility to confront that evil. The UN's languid response to the Rwandan genocide has produced countless studies, reports, and commissions that attempted to piece together what happened and, ultimately, to determine whom to blame for the cowardly act of abandonment. Many of the early investigations affected a diplomatic version of racial profiling and used circumstantial evidence to create a simplistic story that indicted the usual suspect—the United States.[Ibid.]

The mass murders in Kigali quickly spread to the rest of Rwanda from that area. Local authorities in central and southern Rwanda, where most of the Tutsi lived, defied the genocide in the first two weeks. National officials expelled the resisters after April 18 and killed most of them. Other enemies either fell quiet or led the killing aggressively. Murderers were rewarded by officials with food, drink, narcotics and money. Government-sponsored radio stations were already calling on regular citizens in Rwanda to kill their neighbours. The voice of Hutu Power was the private radio station RTLM, established by extremists who surrounded the president. And RTLM was an echo of other extremist media, notably the newspaper Kangura. Once the president's plane was shot down by unknown assailants, the message from RTLM was unmistakable: the Tutsi were to blame; they were the enemy and Rwanda would be better off without them. The killings began almost immediately in Kigali through the night of 6–7 April. Hutu moderates, who were willing to share power, were among the first targeted, along with Tutsi marked for extermination in a campaign that eventually fanned out across the country. Many of the hundreds of thousands of Rwandans who were slaughtered had huddled in churches for sanctuary. Death squads lobbed in grenades. In their frenzy, killers severed the Achilles tendons on the heels of their victims, so they could return and finish the job later. Teachers killed students, neighbours slaughtered neighbours as local officials helped organize the killing.[Thompson, Allan & Annan, Kofi A. 2013. *The media and the Rwanda genocide*. Johannesburg: MTM.]

Over 800,000 civilians were killed within three months. The RPF, meanwhile, resumed fighting, and amid the genocide, civil war erupted. RPF forces had established control over much of the nation, including Kigali, by early July and more than 2 million citizens, almost all Hutus, left Rwanda in response, crowding into refugee camps in the Congo (at the time known as Zaire) and other neighbouring countries. After its victory, the RPF formed, with Pasteur Bizimungu, a Hutu, as president and Paul Kagame, a Tutsi, as vice-president and defence minister, a coalition government close to the one decided at Arusha. The NRMD party of Habyarimana, which had played a crucial role in planning the genocide, was banned and the reference to ethnicity was abolished by a new constitution adopted in 2003. Kagame's election to a 10-year term as Rwanda's president and the country's first-ever parliamentary elections preceded the new constitution. The international community remained mainly on the sidelines during the Rwandan genocide, as in the case of massacres committed in the former Yugoslavia at the same time. Most international news organizations initially misunderstood the nature of the killing in Rwanda, portraying it as the result of tribal warfare, rather than genocide. Much of the international coverage focused on the scramble to evacuate expatriates from the country. In mid-April, when the killing intensified, the volume of news reports declined. Most journalists had left along with the other foreigners. [Ibid.] Except for those who argued for intervention, namely, Nigeria, New Zealand, and the Czech Republic, members of the council bear some moral responsibility. They did not come to recognize the genocide for what it was until after April 21, but at that point, the council had an obligation to try to assemble an intervention force. Yet

many dillydallied and preferred buck-passing and endless Security Council sessions to concerted action. The behaviour of the United States during this period is simply unconscionable. It continued to deny in public that there was a genocide and then actively obstructed the only half-decent intervention plan available because it feared any intervention, by necessity, would include American participation.[Barnett, Michael N. 2002. *Eyewitness to a Genocide: The United Nations and Rwanda*. 1st arg. Cornell University Press.]

A vote of the United Nations Security Council in April 1994 led to the removal of much of the United Nations peacekeeping mission (UNAMIR), creating the previous fall to help the governmental transition under the Arusha agreement. The Security Council voted in mid-May to supply a more powerful military, with more than 5,000 soldiers, as news of the genocide spread. However, by the time the action came on the whole, the genocide had been over for months. In a separate U.N.-approved French invasion, in late June, French forces invaded Rwanda from Zaire. They limited their presence to a "humanitarian region" set up in southwestern Rwanda in the face of the rapid advance of the RPF, saving tens of thousands of Tutsis lives while also aiding some of the plotters of the genocide, who were allies of the French during the Habyarimana administration to escape. Many leading figures of the international community regretted, in the wake of the Rwandan genocide, the general oblivion of the outside world to the crisis and its inability to intervene to deter the massacres from taking place. Just as the old U.N. Secretary-General Boutros Boutros-Ghali told the PBS news program *Frontline*: "Rwanda's failure is 10 times greater than Yugoslavia's failure." The international community, since it was interested in Yugoslavia, was involved. No one in Rwanda was interested. "Later efforts were made to rectify this passivity." The UNAMIR activity was returned to power after the victory of the RFP; it remained in Rwanda until March 1996, as one of the largest humanitarian relief efforts in history. The first conviction for genocide after a trial was released by the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR) in September 1998, finding Jean-Paul Akayesu guilty of actions he committed and supervised as mayor of the Rwandan town of Rwanda. The International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR) in Tanzania was created in October 1994 as an expansion of the International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia (ICTY) in The Hague, the first international tribunal since the 1945-46 Nuremberg Trials, and the first with a mandate to prosecute genocide. In 1995, the ICTR started to prosecute and try several higher-ranking individuals for their role in the genocide in Rwanda; since the location of certain perpetrators is unclear, the procedure was made more difficult. For the next decade and a half, the prosecutions proceeded, including the conviction in 2008 of three former senior Rwandan security and military officials for planning the genocide.

A government was first created, with a Hutu as president, Pasteur Bizimungu as president, and Mr Kagame as his deputy. They fell out, however, and Bizimungu was jailed, while Mr Kagame became president, on charges of inciting ethnic violence. While the killings in Rwanda have stopped, the involvement of Hutu militias in DR Congo has contributed to years of violence, killing up to five million civilians. The Tutsi-led government of Rwanda has now occupied its far larger neighbour twice, claiming it wants to drive out Hutu forces. And a resistance faction of the Congolese Tutsi remains involved, refusing to lay down weapons, claiming that otherwise, their nation will be at risk of genocide. Rwanda remains a profoundly segregated nation fifteen years after the genocide, where distrust and scepticism prevail. The government has made considerable efforts to improve the country and promote reconciliation. The jails are packed with over 100,000 persons convicted of engaging in the genocide. It will take up to 200 years to judge each one individually. To speed up the process, Rwanda used a common method to settle disputes called Gacaca or collective courts to prosecute those accused of intervening in the genocide of 1994. In northern Tanzania, main persons - particularly those suspected of orchestrating the massacre - appear before the International Criminal Tribunal. Yet if Rwanda is to move ahead in its socio-economic growth and to sustain stability, long-term commitment is also required to resolve concerns such as coping with the past, reinforcing the rule of law, and democracy.

We can go in further to take a look at the stakeholders of the peacebuilding process in Rwanda as well as the strengthening of it. This stakeholder community is comprised of victims of genocide as well as vulnerable groups.

Victims who escaped and hid to avoid the murders for weeks and who lived most frequently lost land and belongings, not just relatives and friends. They are still part of the vulnerable groups in the post-genocide phase, given their condition. Victims, in this situation, are those persons who have been wounded or lost a member of their family members since the genocide. The victims are also moderate Hutus and civilians who have been forced to kill when attacked. Rwanda's Tutsi survivors (deceased victims but not deemed stakeholders), outside Rwanda, Tutsi survivors (refugees in neighbouring countries including DR Congo), on all sides, infants and orphans, indigent women who have lost their husbands either because of the genocide or because they are in prison for murder and moderate Hutus living in countries outside of Rwanda. The perpetrators are the ones who murdered or orchestrated the massacres. They can be classified as follows; instigators-organized and scheduled the genocide, Interahamwe - paramilitary force or militia group, Hutu civilians who engaged happily in the killings and Hutu people who had been coerced to kill. A difference may also be made between offenders still to be convicted in prison and those who are either free or who have been released. In addition, a distinction may be made between criminals who feel guilty and those who do not, as a stakeholder impact. The young generation, born after the genocide, did not witness the killings directly. In the peacebuilding process, they are important players as they will build their nation's future. For the government, the stakeholder group mainly consists of The Ministry of Justice, Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Mayors and Sector Coordinators. The government of Rwanda, through Vision 2020, has put in place a policy framework that is expected to transform the country from an agricultural-based economy to an information-rich, knowledge-based society and economy within the next twenty years. This is largely through the GOR's recognition of the role that ICTs can play in accelerating the socio-economic development of the country toward an information and knowledge economy. One of the key objectives of Rwanda's Vision 2020 is to turn the country into an ICT centre of excellence in the region.[Kimanuka, Oscar. 2009. Sub-Saharan Africa's development challenges: A Case Study of Rwanda's Post-Genocide Experience. New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan.]

The NURC founded "forums for reconciliation" in all of the 30 districts of Rwanda to decentralize its work and prevent a top-down approach. Here, a reconciliation forum may be interpreted as a meeting of individuals from all aspects of society to facilitate reconciliation efforts, especially at the level of the community. This strategy has been built to ensure continuous consultation with the grassroots and to engage with local groups daily. The forum is also meant to draw together several different reconciliation parties to enable the reconciliation process to be driven by residents. Furthermore, the establishment of forums was intended to lead to enhancing cooperation and to prevent overlapping of reconciliation efforts in Rwanda, to improve the capacity of reconciliation stakeholders and to develop frameworks for exchanging information and dispute resolution.

The forums are made up of participants selected from several different fields of cultural life. These members, to name just a few, including NGOs, religious leaders, young people, and the military. A committee of ten to fourteen individuals chosen by the members organizes the district platform. Observations from the participants of such forums suggest that these district forums can successfully organize the reconciliation-related efforts of community officials, local and foreign NGOs and governments provided they can be properly prepared and trained. While some may see this as another form of government regulation and presume some political calculations and involvement, it has been characterized by those participating in the district forums as a supportive tool for organizing community-related healing efforts. They have found a space for transparent and critical dialogue at forum sessions, which is an integral component of the transition of true unity and lasting social harmony.

Rwanda has accomplished some remarkable milestones in the peace process at the state level. Reconciliation at the group and citizen levels, however, also poses major obstacles. It is imperative to develop the capacity for community dialogue to overcome the challenges. Almost everyone who intervenes in the reconciliation process in Rwanda believes that the next step of the reconciliation and peace policy should be based solely on group dialogue. It is predicted that the forums for reconciliation will play a major role. Nonetheless, the present state of the forums shows that they need

to be improved. The Danish Institute for Human Rights (DIHR) is an autonomous, national human rights organization designed in line with the United Nations Paris Principles. The DIHR's key goal is to foster and improve human rights awareness on a national, regional and international level, based on the premise that human rights are fundamental, interdependent and interrelated. The key goal of the DIHR in Rwanda is to improve the efforts and cooperation of civil society-based legal assistance in Rwanda. This is achieved when directly liaising with the government of Rwanda. A subsidiary goal is to encourage the creation in Rwanda of a legal aid system or regulation or legislation encompassing civil society and state interventions, while at the same time maintaining the richness and diversity of civil society initiatives already in place. The other major DIHR action was aimed at providing legal protection in ordinary courts in cases of genocide and at building the ability of the Corps of Judicial Defenders and individual defenders of the judiciary. In February 2006, this initiative officially ended when the government transferred the ordinary courts to the current Gacaca authority.

A recent series of workshops that brought together district forum members highlighted the critical need to improve the ability of district forms to enable them to accomplish their function. A variety of problems were found by the participants. A basic concern was a lack of cooperation between the forums and local leadership. The subjects criticized the current relationship between the conference, district, and sector leadership and inadequate cooperation. They regretted the fact that the active presence of elected officials is virtually non-existent in many districts. They also said that there is no time for participants who shape the forum for reconciliation to meet and, for some of them, they realized the lack of ownership and sense of communitarianism among members of the forum. The lack of capacity, such as travel, means of communication, and educational materials, is another serious concern posed by the participants. In addition, there was a suggestion that members are not prepared on what is needed from them for the mediation forums. The participants proposed a range of suggestions of which I agree with, to respond to the challenges and ensure the efficacy of the forum. It includes developing realistic plans to ensure local leadership ownership and regular participation in the reconciliation process, the need to develop input contact channels, improving advice and tracking mechanisms to ensure that the forums are effective, allocating an appropriate budget for reconciliation forums and strengthening their control systems, and equipping forums with the potential to build an atmosphere conducive to community engagement and healing.

In my opinion, the position of the forums at the grassroots is critical in bringing the reconciliation process from the national to the neighbourhood and interpersonal levels, as reconciliation is about rebuilding destroyed relationships between individuals. To ensure that an ecosystem able to accommodate and promote healing is successfully built at the grassroots level, the forums need even further investment instead of seeking to build new mechanisms and so, they need to use current reconciliation forums and improve upon them.

Research Methodology

The mixed-method approach of quantitative and qualitative research method was used in this research article.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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